

Autism Detection using pre-trained models in Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT:

Ensuring high accuracy while working with diseases, such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), is crucial. ASD brings developmental disability to the brain and is also associated with genetic conditions. Some causes of ASD are known, while others are still unknown. Patients with ASD exhibit different behavior, communication, interaction, and learning styles compared to ordinary people. While some patients can live and work like ordinary people without any support, many patients require assistance from others to live their life. Some patients may have advanced conversation skills, while others may be nonverbal. Usually, ASD starts to develop before the age of three, but some children may show symptoms early in the 12-month period. In the first 12 or 24 months, they gain knowledge and skills, but later stop learning, making it difficult to communicate with peers and adults, make new friends, and understand complex concepts. People with ASD are also more likely to experience serious issues such as anxiety, depression, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder compared to those without ASD. Early detection of ASD is crucial as it significantly decreases symptoms and has a high chance of improving the quality of life. Medical tests such as blood tests and symptom checkings are the most common ways of detecting ASD. The symptoms are usually checked by parents or teachers, and healthcare providers.

INTRODUCTION

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurological and developmental disorder that affects how people interact with others, communicate, learn, and behave. Although

autism can be diagnosed at any age, it is described as a “developmental disorder” because symptoms generally appear in the first 2 years of life.

According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), a guide created by the American Psychiatric Association that health care providers use to diagnose mental disorders, people with ASD often have:

- Difficulty with communication and interaction with other people
- Restricted interests and repetitive behaviours
- Symptoms that affect their ability to function in school, work, and other areas of life.

Autism is known as a “spectrum” disorder because there is wide variation in the type and severity of symptoms people experience. People of all genders, races, ethnicities, and economic backgrounds can be diagnosed with ASD. Although ASD can be a lifelong disorder, treatments and services can improve a person’s symptoms and daily functioning. The American Academy of Pediatrics recommends that all children receive screening for autism. Caregivers should talk to their child’s health care provider about ASD screening or evaluation.

Our contributions can be summarised as follows:

1. We classify Autism disease using advanced Neural Network models such as VGG16, Resnet50, Densenet, Inceptionv3, Xception, Mobilenet, and XGBOOST-VGG16, and show which model performs better on this dataset.
2. We propose our Stacking Neural Network model using the aforementioned.
3. We conduct a comparison study on the power usage of well-known pre-trained CNN frameworks on various hardware (i.e., Dell Gaming laptop and Google Colab). Our findings provide insights into how the application’s.

Review of Literature

The list below gives some examples of common types of behaviours in people diagnosed with ASD. Not all people with ASD will have all behaviours.

1.1 Social communication / interaction behaviours may include:

- Making little or inconsistent eye contact
- Appearing not to look at or listen to people who are talking
- Infrequently sharing interest, emotion, or enjoyment of objects or activities (including infrequent pointing at or showing things to others)
- Not responding or being slow to respond to one’s name or to other verbal bids for attention
- Having difficulties with the back and forth of conversation

- Often talking at length about a favourite subject without noticing that others are not interested or without giving others a chance to respond
- Displaying facial expressions, movements, and gestures that do not match what is being said
- Having an unusual tone of voice that may sound sing-song or flat and robot-like
- Having trouble understanding another person's point of view or being unable to predict or understand other people's actions
- Difficulties adjusting behaviours to social situations
- Difficulties sharing in imaginative play or in making friends

1.3.1 Restrictive / repetitive behaviours may include:

- Repeating certain behaviours or having unusual behaviours, such as repeating words or phrases (a behaviour called echolalia)
- Having a lasting intense interest in specific topics, such as numbers, details, or facts
- Showing overly focused interests, such as with moving objects or parts of objects
- Becoming upset by slight changes in a routine and having difficulty with transitions
- Being more sensitive or less sensitive than other people to sensory input, such as light, sound, clothing, or temperature
- People with ASD may also experience sleep problems and irritability.

People on the autism spectrum also may have many strengths, including:

- Being able to learn things in detail and remember information for long periods of time
- Being strong visual and auditory learners
- Excelling in math, science, music, or art

1.2 Causes and related factors:

Researchers don't know the primary causes of ASD, but studies suggest that a person's genes can act together with aspects of their environment to affect development in ways that lead to ASD. Some factors that are associated with an increased likelihood of developing ASD include:

- Having a sibling with ASD
- Having older parents
- Having certain genetic conditions (such as Down syndrome or Fragile X syndrome)
- Having a very low birth weight

1.3 Diagnosing ASD:

Health care providers diagnose ASD by evaluating a person's behaviour and development. ASD can usually be reliably diagnosed by age 2. It is important to seek an evaluation as soon as possible. The earlier ASD is diagnosed, the sooner treatments and services can begin.

1.3.1 Diagnosis in young children:

Diagnosis in young children is often a two-stage process.

Stage 1: General developmental screening during well-child checkups

Every child should receive well-child check-ups with a paediatrician or an early childhood health care provider. The American Academy of Pediatrics recommends that all children receive screening for developmental delays at their 9-, 18-, and 24- or 30-month well-child visits, with specific autism screenings at their 18- and 24-month well-child visits. A child may receive additional screening if they have a higher likelihood of ASD or developmental problems. Children with a higher likelihood of ASD include those who have a family member with ASD, show some behaviours that are typical of ASD, have older parents, have certain genetic conditions, or who had a very low birth weight.

Considering caregivers' experiences and concerns is an important part of the screening process for young children. The health care provider may ask questions about the child's behaviours and evaluate those answers in combination with information from ASD screening tools and clinical observations of the child. Read more about screening instruments on the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) website. If a child shows developmental differences in behaviour or functioning.

Stage 2: Additional diagnostic evaluation

It is important to accurately detect and diagnose children with ASD as early as possible, as this will shed light on their unique strengths and challenges. Early detection also can help caregivers determine which services, educational programs, and behavioural therapies are most likely to be helpful for their child.

A team of health care providers who have experience diagnosing ASD will conduct the diagnostic evaluation. This team may include child neurologists, developmental paediatricians, speech-language pathologists, child psychologists and

psychiatrists, educational specialists, and occupational therapists.

The diagnostic evaluation is likely to include:

- Medical and neurological examinations
- Assessment of the child's cognitive abilities
- Assessment of the child's language abilities
- Observation of the child's behaviour
- An in-depth conversation with the child's caregivers about the child's behaviour and development
- Assessment of age-appropriate skills needed to complete daily activities independently, such as eating, dressing, and toileting

Because ASD is a complex disorder that sometimes occurs with other illnesses or learning disorders, the comprehensive evaluation may include:

- Blood tests
- Hearing test

The evaluation may lead to a formal diagnosis and recommendations for treatment.

1.3.2 Diagnosis in older children and adolescents:

Caregivers and teachers are often the first to recognize ASD symptoms in older children and adolescents who attend school. The school's special education team may perform an initial evaluation and then recommend that a child undergo additional evaluation with their primary health care provider or a health care provider who specialise in ASD.

A child's caregivers may talk with these health care providers about their child's social difficulties, including problems with subtle communication. For example, some children may have problems understanding tone of voice, facial

expressions, or body language. Older children and adolescents may have trouble understanding figures of speech, humour, or sarcasm. They also may have trouble forming friendships with peers.

Diagnosis in adults:

Diagnosing ASD in adults is often more difficult than diagnosing ASD in children. In adults, some ASD symptoms can overlap with symptoms of other mental health

disorders, such as anxiety disorder or attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

Adults who notice signs of ASD should talk with a health care provider and ask for a referral for an ASD evaluation. Although evaluation for ASD in adults is still being refined, adults may be referred to a neuropsychologist, psychologist, or psychiatrist who has experience with ASD. The expert will ask about:

- Social interaction and communication challenges
- Sensory issues
- Repetitive behaviours
- Restricted interests

The evaluation also may include a conversation with caregivers or other family members to learn about the person's early developmental history, which can help ensure an accurate diagnosis. Receiving a correct diagnosis of ASD as an adult can help a person understand past challenges, identify personal strengths, and find the right kind of help. Studies are underway to determine the types of services and supports that are most helpful for improving the functioning and community integration of autistic transition-age youth and adults.

Treatments and therapies:

Treatment for ASD should begin as soon as possible after diagnosis. Early treatment for ASD is important as proper care and services can reduce individuals' difficulties while helping them build on their strengths and learn new skills.

People with ASD may face a wide range of issues, which means that there is no single best treatment for ASD. Working closely with a health care provider is an important part of finding the right combination of treatment and services.

Medication:

A health care provider may prescribe medication to treat specific symptoms. With medication, a person with ASD may have fewer problems with:

- Irritability
- Aggression
- Repetitive behaviour
- Hyperactivity
- Attention problems
- Anxiety and depression

Traditional Image Processing Techniques

Edge Detection Algorithms: Sobel, Prewitt, and Canny edge detectors are often applied to highlight boundaries, including cracks.

Thresholding Techniques: Simple thresholding or adaptive thresholding can be used to segment cracks based on intensity differences.

Morphological Operations: Techniques like dilation and erosion help refine crack boundaries.

Fig 2.1 Edge Detection Architecture

Drawbacks

- Limited ability to handle complex scenarios and diverse crack patterns.
- Sensitivity to variations in lighting conditions and image quality.

Proposed Methodology in Machine Learning Approaches

Support Vector Machines (SVM): SVMs are used for binary classification tasks, distinguishing between cracked and non-cracked regions based on extracted features.

Random Forests: Random Forest classifiers can be trained on features extracted from concrete images to classify cracks.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN): KNN algorithms use proximity-based classification, assigning labels based on the majority class of neighboring data points.

Drawbacks

- Limited ability to handle complex scenarios and diverse crack patterns.
- Sensitivity to variations in lighting conditions and image quality.

2. Hybrid Approaches

Feature Fusion Techniques: Integrating features from multiple sources, such as texture, color, and shape, can enhance the performance of crack detection algorithms.

Drawbacks

- Increased complexity in algorithm design and implementation.
- Require careful tuning of parameters to achieve optimal performance.

3. Region-Based Methods

Region Growing: This method starts with seed points and grows regions based on predefined criteria, which can be applied to identify and classify cracks.

Graph Cut: Graph-based methods can be employed for segmenting images into regions, aiding in the identification of cracks.

Drawbacks:

- Sensitive to variations in image resolution and scale.
- May struggle with irregular-shaped cracks or those in complex backgrounds.

4. Transfer Learning

Pre-trained Models: Leveraging pre-trained models, such as those trained on large image datasets like ImageNet, and fine-tuning them for crack detection tasks can be effective, especially when labeled data is limited.

Drawbacks:

- Transferability may be limited if the pre-trained model is not sufficiently related to the crack detection task.
- Fine-tuning may be necessary to adapt the model to the specific characteristics of concrete cracks.

Fig 2 Transfer Learning

5. Heuristic-Based Approaches

Texture Analysis: Analyzing textural properties of concrete surfaces can reveal patterns indicative of cracks.

Rule-Based Systems: Rule-based approaches use predefined rules and conditions to identify and classify cracks based on specific characteristics.

Drawbacks:

- Highly dependent on the accuracy of predefined rules and heuristics.
- May struggle with capturing the complexity of crack patterns in real-world scenarios.

It's important to note that the effectiveness of these algorithms depends on factors such as the quality and diversity of the dataset, the characteristics of the concrete surfaces, and the specific requirements of the application. Additionally, the field is dynamic, and new algorithms and improvements are continuously being developed to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of crack detection and classification in concrete structures.

Pretrained Autism Model

Designing a data flow for Autism Detection using pre-trained models involves several stages, from data acquisition to model deployment.

Here's a simplified overview of the data flow design:

Classification Models and Fine Tuning

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a subfield of conventional Neural Network, which comprises three elements: one or more convolutional layers, a pooling layer, and one fully connected layer. The first element is the fundamental building block of the CNN model and calculates the dot product between the kernel and a portion of the input image. The kernel size is relatively smaller than the size of the input image, while the kernel dimension is similar to the input image size.

Xception:

The Xception model was created by Chollet, a Google researcher. Xception is a deep convolutional neural network that uses a linear combination of residual connections and depth-wise separable convolution. The Inception model was used as a foundation for this unique deep neural network design, which substitutes depth-wise separable convolution for the Inception model's inception layers. The

architecture is less complex and more effective than existing deep convolutional neural networks due to the idea of developing it with fully depth-wise separable convolution. To further optimize the model, we included the Flatten() layer, BatchNormalization(), a Dense layer with 128 neurons and Relu function, followed by BatchNormalization(), and a final Dense layer with one neuron and sigmoid function, after downloading the base model. Finally, using the Stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizer and a learning rate of 0.0001 on 2936 sample images for 30 epochs, we fine-tuned the model. The trainable parameters of the Xception model are 33,853,225.

VGG-16:

VGG-16 is the most advanced deep neural network for interpreting visual input. It is considered one of the best architectures for vision models to date, and it won the 2014 ILSVR (Imagenet) competition.

We utilized the stacking ensemble learning approach to develop our proposed system, which involved logistic regression as the meta-learner and heterogeneous weak learners as the base models. Inceptionv3, Xception, Densenet, Mobilenet, Resnet-50, and VGG-16 were used as the heterogeneous base models, which took in three-dimensional images as inputs. The data separation process differed from that of traditional models, with 60% of the data being used for training, 10% for validation, and 30% for testing. This modification was necessary to avoid overfitting during the meta-learner training phase. The predicted dataset from Level 0 already contained a probability of expected values, enabling the meta-learner to provide accurate probabilities from Level 0.

To prevent overfitting, the final model (meta-learner) was trained using both the validation dataset and the outputs. The level1 prediction was the ultimate result. The stacking ensemble model produced a final model (meta-learner) by using the predicted results from several other models. The disadvantage of the typical stacking ensemble method is that it employs the same various models for the base model, which leads to similar estimates. If the basic model performs poorly on the dataset, there is a high possibility that the final output will be inferior.

However, the single neural network model demonstrates bias and volatility toward the dataset. As a result, different models were chosen when constructing the base model. The architecture is divided into two levels: Level 0 and Level1, as shown in Figure. Inceptionv3, Xception, Densenet, Mobilenet, Resnet-50, and VGG-16 models are used to construct Level 0. The six submodels each make six predictions concurrently

after learning the data pattern. Each model employed in Level 0 contributes equally to the overall model. Logistic regression is used to build Level 1, also known as the metalearner.

The meta-learner at Level 1 is fed the Level 0 projected outputs as input. Based on the anticipated Level 0 outputs, the meta-learner estimates the weighted outputs best. A model that can quickly learn a pattern or adjust to different datasets with a small amount of training data is referred to as a “meta learner.” It learns patterns of the outputs derived from the six models. As a result, the model can learn completely new data quite effectively and produce acceptable output. The parameter of this model is a combination of six transfer learnings’ learnable parameters.

Fig 4.1. Proposed Architecture for Autism Disease classification.

Fig 4.1.1 Framework of the proposed recognition system.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have established a strong reputation in the field of image data processing, producing superior results compared to traditional methods. However, they require enormous data for the training phase, sometimes socially referred to as data-hungry algorithms especially training from scratch. However, transfer learning (TL) has solved this problem to a very large extent, where a pre-trained model is retrained to perform a specific task with fewer data samples. Pre-trained deep learning models provide substantial benefits in artificial intelligence and machine learning. These models save practitioners time and computing resources by providing powerful starting points for numerous tasks, leveraging knowledge from prolonged training on big and diverse datasets. The selection of the best TL model is crucial, as different models may perform better or worse depending on the dataset. One approach to address this enigma is employing top networks as a whole to achieve good results. In this research, we employed six widely recognized pre-trained models, ResNet34, ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19, AlexNet, and MobileNetv2 - to evaluate their performance in the detection of autistic disorders based on facial images. To this end, we employed the ResNets models with two different settings of the ASD dataset, utilizing image sizes of 124×124 and 248×248 pixels to investigate the relationship between performance and image size. The training of all these pre-trained models was completed in three batches of epochs, with each model undergoing a total of 5 initial epochs, followed by a selective learning rate for an additional seven epochs, during which all layers were frozen except for the last two. Finally, each model was unfrozen for further training for a total of 8 epochs. This approach allows the models to learn from the data more thoroughly and efficiently and allows for the fine-tuning of the models using the selective learning rate. The block architecture of the proposed methodology is illustrated in Figure.

Fig 4.1.2 Flowchart of the proposed method.

Image analysis can classify autistic people by identifying distinguishing visual traits. Here, facial expressions are important since they reveal emotions and social interactions. Eye gaze patterns are important because autistic people may have unusual eye contact. Body language, including gestures and postural clues, helps explain autism's peculiar behaviours. A holistic view of an individual's relationships comes from contextual awareness, which includes social and environmental aspects. Recognition of repetitive actions, a prevalent autistic feature, and social interaction dynamics aid classification. Machine learning and deep learning can extract and evaluate these properties from photos, revealing autism's complex spectrum. This research must be sensitive to autism heterogeneity and follow ethical norms for visual data classification.

The goal of this research is to train and identify the best model based on the given images and subsequently propose the most effective model for the early detection of autism spectrum disorder (ASD). A description of the pre-trained networks

4.1 DATABASE DESIGN:

The database design for the "Autism Detection using pre-trained models using CNN (VGG19)" project encompasses organizing and structuring data to efficiently store and manage information essential for autism detection. The database comprises several key entities, including 'Patient', 'Medical History', 'Neuroimaging Data', and 'Diagnosis', each with their respective attributes capturing patient demographics, medical records, neuroimaging information, and diagnostic results. For instance, the 'Patient' entity stores patient identifiers, while 'Medical History' records past diagnoses and treatments. 'Neuroimaging Data' contains details of neuroimaging scans, and 'Diagnosis' captures results obtained from the pre-trained CNN model VGG19. Relationships between these entities facilitate the flow of information, such as the one-to-many relationship between 'Patient' and 'Medical History', indicating multiple medical records per patient. The database design ensures data integrity, accessibility, and scalability, supporting the effective implementation and evaluation of the autism detection system leveraging pre-trained CNN models like VGG19.

About Dataset:

- Dataset contain two different files of directories each segmented under consolidated, train, train & valid images.
- All the three directories contain 1000+ images segmented under Autistic & Non autistic.

- Presence of the directories helps the project in detecting Autism under pre-trained models

Moreover, these relationships clarify the interactions within the system. For example, the 'Patient' entity's one-to-many relationship with 'Neuroimaging Data' signifies that a patient can undergo multiple scans. Additionally, the one-to-one relationship between 'Neuroimaging Data' and 'Diagnosis' indicates that each scan corresponds to a single diagnosis. Overall, the ER Diagram provides a structured representation of the database schema, essential for organizing data and facilitating effective implementation and evaluation of the autism detection system leveraging pre-trained CNN models like VGG19.

4.2 Input Design

The input design for the "Autism Detection using pre-trained models using CNN (VGG19)" project involves defining the parameters and data inputs required to effectively utilize the pre-trained model for autism detection. This includes gathering neuroimaging data such as MRI or fMRI scans, which serves as the primary input for the VGG19 model. Additionally, demographic information about the patients, including age, gender, and any relevant medical

Fig 4.3 Input Dataset

4.3 Output Design:

The output design for the "Autism Detection using pre-trained models using CNN (VGG19)" project focuses on presenting the results of the autism detection process in a clear and interpretable manner. Upon processing the input neuroimaging data through

the pre-trained VGG19 model, the output design aims to provide diagnostic information indicating the likelihood or presence of autism spectrum disorder (ASD). This output may include probability scores or confidence levels assigned by the model to indicate the certainty of the diagnosis. Additionally, the output design may involve visual representations such as heatmaps highlighting regions of interest in the neuroimaging data that contribute to the model's decision. The output design ensures that the diagnostic results are presented in a format that is easily understandable and actionable for healthcare professionals, facilitating informed clinical decision-making and patient management strategies.

Fig 4.4 Output Images

SYSTEM TESTING AND IMPLEMENTATION

System Testing:

In recent years, deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been used extensively in computer vision, showing powerful discriminative capabilities while maintaining high performance levels. As deep learning networks have established themselves as a promising model for facial recognition and CNNs have been used as the deep learning tool in almost all facial recognition systems, our research focused on a deep-learning-based solution. In a recent comparative study of popular deep-learning architectures for facial recognition, Gwyn reported that VGG16/VGG19 showed the highest accuracy levels of image recognition; as such, we further focused our study using VGG16-based deep learning.

Transfer learning is a machine learning method where a model developed for one task is reused as the starting point for a model on a second task, and is a popular

approach in deep learning. Visual Geometry Group (VGG) is a CNN model proposed by Simonyan and Zisserman that achieved 92.7% accuracy, placing it in the top-five in test accuracy on ImageNet, a dataset of over 14 million images belonging to 1000 classes. VGGFace is a facial image dataset that contains 2.6 million images of different people contributed by the Visual Geometry Group. Tensorflow is an end-to-end open-source platform for machine learning. It has a comprehensive, flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries, and community resources. Keras is the high-level API of Tensorflow. Keras-VGGFace is an Oxford VGGFace implementation using Keras Functional Framework v2+. A VGG16 model pre-trained with VGGFace is provided in Keras-VGGFace. Thus, VGG16 was adopted for this research as the pre-trained model for transfer learning.

Our research was conducted in two major focus areas:

1. The feasibility and quality of applying deep learning in the detection of ASD in children using 2D facial images.
2. Understanding the significance of race factors in ASD detection or diagnosis using deep learning and facial images.

After collecting the dataset from the mentioned sources, we will use our dataset to train, test and validate our model. The methodology that we use will be as follows:

- 1) Load the training dataset: We will start by first training our dataset. The two files in our dataset have the names "Non_Autistic.135.jpg" and "Autistic.391.jpg," with the terms "Non_Autistic.135" and "Autistic.391" denoting the type (whether the person is autistic or not) and the second word denoting the image number, respectively.
- 2) Load Test Dataset: Included in our dataset are the files "Non_Autistic.135.jpg and Autistic.391.jpg."
- 3) Multilayer neural networks will be used as deep neural networks.
- 4) Convolutional Neural Networks will be utilised because the dataset only contains pictures. A method to separate the data into distinct groups is the CNN classification. A picture will pass through a variety of convolutional layers and filters each time it is processed.
- 5) Model Preparation: Next, we'll set up the model by taking the following actions.
- 6) Next, we'll discuss hyperparameters.
- 7) The output layer is then flattened to one dimension.
- 8) A completely There will also be an additional connected layer with 512 hidden units and ReLU activation.
- 9) The dropout rate will then be increased by 0.5.
- 10) A final sigmoid layer will then be added for classification.
- 11) Data Preparation: In order to create a matrix, we will prepare the data and extract the necessary information from the images.

12) Getting ready the training dataset:

- a) Training Generator: In this section, the train data will be prepared and generated.
- b) Validation Generator: Using the verified data, we will develop a validation generator to filter the data and assure the performance quality.
- c) Validation data: Information used to assess any model metrics and the loss at the conclusion of each epoch. These data won't be used to train the model.

13) Model Fitting: At this point, we'll train the data using a predetermined batch size and number of epochs.

14) Creating a testing generator will allow us to generate the test dataset from the test photos that have already been imported.

15) Prediction: Using the model that was previously assessed, we will now predict the outcome for the test dataset.

16) There will be the following results: The image's name is:- actual name (image name 0 or 1); for instance, autistic.127.jpg(1); 0/1 is a prediction in this case.

17) Our forecasts will be kept in the submission_13010030.csv file. This file includes the anticipated outcome, and we will further determine its.

18) correctness, precision, etc.

System implementation:

The dataset has been taken from Kaggle which is publicly accessible and we also customized the dataset by adding several images of toddlers. The necessary libraries are included such as Tensor Flow, Keras, NumPy, Pandas, matplotlib, and sklearn. Google Drive is mounted to access the dataset. Then, prepare the data by normalizing the pixel values and resizing the photos to a uniform size of 224x224 pixels. Image labeling is done as 'Autistic' and 'Non Autistic' by assigning 1 and 0 respectively. The ratio of the training set to the validation set is 80:20. Hyperparameters 'epoch' and 'batch size' is set to 23 and 64 respectively.

A model is trained when it is shown how to categorise or predict something using existing preliminary data. To begin with, the divided original dataset is used to create the train dataset, which will be used to train the model. We will create a validation generator to screen out the data and utilise the verified data to ensure performance quality after preparing and creating the train data. The validation data are the data used to assess any model metrics and the loss at the conclusion of each epoch. These data won't be used to train the model. After using the validation dataset to judge the performance of our model, we will train the data for a particular number of epochs and batch size. We evaluated using a batch size of 12 with 10 epochs to train our model. We trained two models, in which one is based on VGG16 and the other is based on VGG19. Utilising the validation dataset, we will compute the evaluation metrics to assess the performance of our model at the end of each epoch.

The results of the deep learning models are presented in this section, and the significant results of developing system are declared.

Experimental Setup: The experiment was executed on different libraries of python and hardware devices for developing an intelligent autism detection system (ADS).

Evaluation metrics

Evaluation metrics are used to assess how effectively a statistical or machine learning model is functioning. The machine learning models or algorithms employed in each project must be evaluated. This study uses different types of performance evaluation metrics for the three pretrained models such as accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity and confusion matrix. A confusion matrix is a type of measure of classification performance that represents a table of the true and false values of the testing results. A model may be assessed using a variety of different assessment metrics. These consist of measurements such as classification accuracy, logarithmic loss, confusion matrix, and others. When we talk about accuracy, we usually mean classification accuracy, which is the proportion of successful predictions to all input data. Logarithmic loss, commonly referred to as log loss, is used to penalise incorrect classifications. A confusion matrix creates a matrix for us and provides a summary of the model's overall performance. In this work, we have used evaluation metrics like Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, and Precision to evaluate the performance of our model.

```

20/20 [=====] - 80s 3s/step - loss: 1.7290 - accuracy: 0.4779 - val_loss: 0.6782 - val_accuracy: 0.5400
Epoch 2/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.6865 - accuracy: 0.5524 - val_loss: 0.6665 - val_accuracy: 0.6100
Epoch 3/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.6851 - accuracy: 0.5615 - val_loss: 0.6507 - val_accuracy: 0.5900
Epoch 4/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.6503 - accuracy: 0.6100 - val_loss: 0.6279 - val_accuracy: 0.6600
Epoch 5/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.6148 - accuracy: 0.6609 - val_loss: 0.6053 - val_accuracy: 0.6200
Epoch 6/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.5872 - accuracy: 0.6960 - val_loss: 0.5675 - val_accuracy: 0.6800
Epoch 7/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.5527 - accuracy: 0.7236 - val_loss: 0.5801 - val_accuracy: 0.7300
Epoch 8/100
20/20 [=====] - 38s 2s/step - loss: 0.5566 - accuracy: 0.7086 - val_loss: 0.5462 - val_accuracy: 0.7200
Epoch 9/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.5356 - accuracy: 0.7252 - val_loss: 0.6339 - val_accuracy: 0.6800
Epoch 10/100
20/20 [=====] - 37s 2s/step - loss: 0.5267 - accuracy: 0.7358 - val_loss: 0.5123 - val_accuracy: 0.7400
Epoch 11/100

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Accuracy: Accuracy is a common evaluation statistic for classification problems. It displays the percentage of all forecasts that result in accurate predictions.

Sensitivity: Sensitivity provides the true positive rate (TPR), which is the ratio of

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{FP + FN + TP + TN} \times 100\%,$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FN} \times 100\%,$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \times 100\%,$$

genuine positives to all positives.

Specificity: Specificity is the proportion of genuine negatives that the model correctly identifies. This means that more real negatives, often known as false positives since they were previously believed to be positive, would be recorded.

where TP is the True Positive, FP is the False Positive, TN is the True Negative, and FN is the False Negative. Specificity is the capacity of the model to correctly identify the normal children, and sensitivity is the capacity of the model to correctly identify autistic children.

Precision: Precision (either rightly or wrongly) is the ratio of correctly classified positive samples (True Positive) to all positively classified samples.

Precision = True Positive / True Positive + False Positive

Fig 5.2 Final Output

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we suggested a comprehensive computerised approach for face image-based autism identification. This study used a Convolutional Neural Network with transfer learning to create a deep learning-based online interface for identifying autism. The CNN architecture has the right models to extract the facial landmarks, which can classify faces into autistic and non-autistic types. This is done by producing sequences of facial characteristics and calculating the distance 805 between facial features. Parents and physicians will find it easier to recognise ASD in children with the help of this sort of software. Children with autism may gain from having a correct diagnosis of their condition by picking an appropriate therapy route. With VGG16 as its pre-trained model, the model has a precision of 90% and an accuracy of 84%. This study addresses a gap in the literature by screening young children for ASD using facial photos. Clinical observations that children with ASD and normally developing children have distinct facial characteristics are supported by the study's findings. We are confident that this computer vision method will help address the main issues that lead to racial disparity in the diagnosis or screening of ASD, such as the subjectivity of screening or diagnosis, the difficulty in obtaining access to skilled medical care, and the financial struggles families face globally, particularly in developing countries.

Future work:

In the future, we plan to develop a mobile app for identifying children with autism. The users can capture a set of facial images of children and input them into the app. This app determines the probability of autism for each image, and then provides the average probability of autism for all images. In addition, we plan to perform statistical tests and sensitivity analysis to test the robustness and stability of our algorithms in the future work. We also plan to collaborate with kindergartens, rehabilitation centers for children with autism, and child psychology clinics in hospitals. Kindergarten teachers who observe a child with abnormal behavior can use this app to detect whether this child has autism. If the test result is autism, the child's parents can be reminded to send this child to the children's psychological clinic at the hospital for professional examination. By collaborating with the Rehabilitation Center for Children with Autism and the Child Psychology Clinic, we will obtain a lot of facial images of children with autism, and then train the models of the proposed method to improve its performance.

CHAPTER 7

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